
Research Article

Validation of the name *Habenaria subalpina* M.W.Chase, X.H.Jin & Schuit. (Orchidaceae)

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Abstract: The name *Habenaria subalpina* M.W.Chase, X.H.Jin & Schuit. (Orchidaceae), previously published invalidly, is validated here through the provision of the required full and direct reference to the replaced synonym.

Keywords: China, ICN, *Habenaria*, *Herminium*, Invalid name, new name

Introduction

To resolve the polyphyletic nature of *Habenaria* Willd. demonstrated by several phylogenetic studies (Jin et al., 2014, 2017; Ngugi et al., 2020), Chase et al. (2026) recently broadened the circumscription of the genus to include species formerly placed in *Cooktownia* D.L.Jones, *Diplomeris* D.Don, *Herminium* L., *Pecteilis* Raf., and *Peristylus* Blume. Earlier taxonomic treatments had already merged *Androcorys* Schltr., *Bhutanthera* Renz, *Frigidorchis* Z.J.Liu & S.C.Chen, and *Porolabium* Tang & F.T.Wang into *Herminium* (Raskoti et al., 2016, 2017), while *Bonatea* Willd., *Centrostigma* Schltr., *Platycoryne* Rchb.f., and *Roeperocharis* Rchb.f. were synonymized under *Habenaria* by Bytebier (2015).

More recently, Chase et al. (2026) proposed *Habenaria subalpina* M.W.Chase, X.H.Jin & Schuit. as a replacement name for *Herminium chloranthum* Tang & F.T.Wang (Tang & Wang 1940). However, this name was not validly published because the replaced synonym was not accompanied by a full and direct reference, as required under Art. 41.5 of the ICN (Turland et al. 2025). The name is therefore validated here through the inclusion of the necessary full and direct reference to the replaced synonym.

Nomenclature

Habenaria subalpina M.W.Chase, X.H.Jin & Schuit. ex Kottaim., *nom. nov.*

≡ *Herminium chloranthum* Tang & F.T.Wang, Bull. Fan Mem. Inst. Biol. Bot. 10: 34. 1940.

≡ *Habenaria subalpina* M.W.Chase, X.H.Jin & Schuit., *Phytotaxa* 752(2): 173. 2026, *nom. inval.*

Type: CHINA. Yunnan, Shangri-La (Zhongdian County), 3000 m, 5 July 1937, *T.T. Yu 11920* (Holotype: KUN; Isotype: AMES [AMES00104951!], PE).

Etymology: The specific epithet '*subalpina*' was proposed by Chase et al. (2026) because only a few species of the predominantly subtropical and tropical genus *Habenaria* occur in high alpine habitats.

Distribution: China and Nepal (Chen et al., 2009; Raskoti, 2015; Raskoti et al., 2019).

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